

THE BALI PROVINCIAL DPRD'S COMMISSION IV IMPLEMENTS ADAPTIVE GOVERNANCE IN RESPONSE TO EDUCATIONAL DISPARITIES IN REMOTE AREAS THROUGH THE CIPP MODEL

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the implementation of adaptive governance by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to educational disparities in remote areas using the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) evaluation model. This research employs a descriptive qualitative approach, with data collected through in-depth interviews, field observations, and documentation. Informants were selected purposively based on their relevance to the research focus. The findings reveal that educational inequality in remote areas of Bali is a structural issue influenced by limited infrastructure, uneven distribution of resources, and socio-economic conditions. From the context aspect, there is a significant gap between ideal conditions and field realities. From the input aspect, resources are quantitatively adequate but not optimally distributed or utilized. In terms of process, policy implementation has shifted toward a more participatory and field-based approach, although it has not yet been systematically institutionalized. Meanwhile, from the product aspect, policies have produced initial impacts such as increased attention and educational assistance, but have not significantly reduced disparities. Overall, the implementation of adaptive governance remains in a transitional phase toward a more adaptive, responsive, and sustainable governance system.

Keywords: *adaptive governance, educational inequality, remote areas, CIPP model, education policy, Bali DPRD*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental right of every citizen, as mandated by Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, which affirms the state's obligation to ensure equal access to quality education. Education serves not only as a means of transferring knowledge but also as a process of shaping the mindset and character of society in line with current developments. Therefore, an integrated education system is needed through collaboration between the government, schools, and the community to achieve the national goal of improving the nation's life. However, the reality on the ground shows that inequality in access and quality of education persists, especially in remote areas. This phenomenon also occurs in Bali Province, which, despite being known as a region with a high level of development, still faces inter-regional educational disparities. Data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) of Bali Province in 2024 recorded an average length of schooling (RLS) of 9.54 years, which is still below the target of 12 years of compulsory education. The disparity is clearly visible between districts/cities, where areas such as Denpasar and Badung have reached more than 10 years, while areas such as Karangasem and Bangli are still below 8 years.

This situation is further exacerbated by limited educational infrastructure, uneven distribution of teaching staff, and socio-economic factors. In remote areas such as Kintamani (Bangli) and Munti Gunung (Karangasem), students face obstacles such as long distances, minimal school facilities, and high dropout rates. Furthermore, teacher-to-student ratios in remote areas, which range from 1:35 to 1:40, indicate a high teacher workload and impact the quality of learning. The government has implemented various policies such as the School Operational Assistance (BOS), the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP), the Special Allocation Fund (DAK), and the 12-year compulsory education program. However, the implementation of these policies still faces obstacles, particularly in terms of targeting accuracy, resource distribution, and adaptability to local conditions. This indicates that the main problem lies not only in the policy itself but also in the governance of its implementation.

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In this context, Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD plays a strategic role in carrying out legislative, budgetary, and oversight functions in the education sector. As an institution that acts as a policy guardian, Commission IV is required to ensure that education policies are implemented fairly, inclusively, and on target, especially for communities in remote areas. *adaptive governance* is relevant to addressing these issues, as it emphasizes flexibility, cross-actor collaboration, and the ability to adapt policies to local conditions. To evaluate the effectiveness of this approach, this study uses the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model, which allows for a comprehensive analysis of education policy. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the implementation of *adaptive governance* by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to educational disparities in remote areas in a more systematic and in-depth manner.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Replication of previous research plays an essential role in strengthening the validity and reliability of scientific findings. According to Kerlinger (2006), replication is a crucial pillar of the scientific process because "knowledge can only be considered valid if its results can be replicated by other researchers under comparable conditions." Through the replication process, researchers can test the consistency of research results in different contexts, including time, location, and subject characteristics. Similarly, Creswell (2018) emphasized that replication allows researchers to gain a deeper understanding of the variables that influence research results, while ensuring that the theory used remains relevant to current social changes and public policy. Thus, replication is not merely a form of mechanical repetition, but rather an evaluative and reflective scientific process that strengthens the credibility of knowledge and broadens the context of its application. In this study, entitled "The Implementation of Adaptive Governance by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in Responding to Inequality of Access to Education in Remote Areas as Perceived from the CIPP Model," the author uses several previous studies as scientific references to strengthen the theoretical and conceptual foundation of the study. These research documents were selected based on their relevance to the themes of adaptive governance, public policy, and equitable access to education in remote areas. The following are some of the previous studies used as references:

Table 1 Previous Research

NO	Name Researchers	Research Title	Research result	Research Similarities	Research Differences
1	Ika Widiastuti (2025)	<i>Assessing the Impact of Education Policies in Indonesia: Challenges, Achievements, and Future Direction.</i>	The study's findings indicate that from 2014 to 2024, Indonesia's education sector has made significant progress in terms of increasing student enrollment, decreasing illiteracy rates, and increasing access to inclusive education. However, significant challenges remain. The most prominent are regional disparities, limited infrastructure in remote areas, and uneven teacher	Both studies have quite fundamental similarities in their focus, namely that they both highlight the problem of inequality in access to education and the effectiveness of government policies in responding to this issue.	While previous research has used a general policy valuation approach, highlighting the achievements and challenges of national education policy, this study employs the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model to assess the effectiveness of adaptive governance principles in addressing educational disparities. This model allows for a

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			<p>distribution. Furthermore, Widiastututi highlighted the fact that education policy implementation often does not reflect local needs. Consequently, outcomes are not always optimal in regions with diverse social and geographic characteristics.</p>		<p>more structured and evaluative analysis of all policy stages, from the context of the problem to the outcomes achieved.</p>
2	<p>Ida Wahyu Wijayanti¹, Firtz Hotman Syahmahita Damanik², Carlos Lazaro Prawirosastro³ (2024)</p>	<p>Education Access Gap in Remote Areas: Policy Analysis and Alternatives Solution</p>	<p>This research also highlights that most remote areas still struggle to maintain the continuity of teaching and learning due to a lack of supporting facilities and educational technology. Furthermore, there is a tendency for national education policies to not fully adapt to the geographic and social conditions of the communities in these areas. As a recommendation, this study emphasizes the importance of implementing an adaptive governance approach in the education sector.</p>	<p>The primary focus of both studies is the same: highlighting the problem of inadequate access to education in remote areas. Both stem from concerns that there are still disparities in the quality and equity of education between urban and rural or remote areas in Indonesia. Furthermore, both studies emphasize the importance of public policy and governance in addressing this issue. According to this and previous studies, educational problems are not only technical (such as a lack of facilities or teachers), but also structural</p>	<p>The main differences lie in the level of analysis and institutional focus: previous studies examined educational disparities nationally and were generally descriptive, while this study specifically analyzes the adaptive role of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to educational disparities in remote areas. Furthermore, this study uses the CIPP evaluation model as its analytical framework, which was not used in previous studies.</p>

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				and policy-based, requiring changes in governance.	
3	Yudha Maya Septiana ¹ , Solfema Solfema ² , Lili Dasa Putri ³ (2024)	Efforts to Equalize Education in Remote Areas	This study examines the government's strategy for equalizing access to education in remote areas, primarily through improving school infrastructure and distributing teaching staff. The results indicate that the equalization program has not been fully effective due to budget constraints and low policy adaptation at the regional level. The researchers recommend implementing adaptive governance principles to make education policies more responsive to the social and geographic conditions of remote areas.	Both studies focused on unequal access to education in remote areas and the importance of implementing adaptive governance in education policy. Both also highlighted that education problems are not solely caused by infrastructure factors, but also by the low effectiveness of public policies and weak coordination between government agencies.	The difference lies in the scope and focus of the analysis. While previous research generally discussed efforts to equalize education at the national level, this study specifically analyzes the role of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to unequal access to education, using the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) evaluation model as the primary analytical framework.
4	Chairul Anwar ¹ , Laili Komariyah ² , Ahmad Aznem ³ , Hasbar ⁴ , Lidyawati Tandi Payung ⁵ , Agus Heri Kesuma ⁶ (2025)	Evaluation of Inclusive Education Policy in Indonesia: CIPP Approach and Social Justice Perspective	This study evaluates inclusive education policies in Indonesia using the CIPP model. Contextually, policies have been designed to ensure access for all children, including children with special needs (ABK), but structural and cultural challenges persist. Inputs, including teacher resources, curriculum, and	The current and previous research share significant similarities. Both highlight the issue of inequality or barriers to access to education for vulnerable groups; your research focuses on remote areas in Bali, while this study emphasizes education for	Despite their similar focus on educational access and the use of the CIPP model, there are several clear differences between this study and previous research. This study focuses on the role of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in adaptive governance, focusing on how the legislative body responds to

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			<p>facilities, are suboptimal. Implementation in schools is hampered by the understanding and commitment of educators. Meanwhile, outcomes show that despite efforts to increase access, many ABK still experience learning difficulties. The study recommends improving teacher training, facilities, stakeholder commitment, and regular evaluation to make inclusive education more effective.</p>	<p>children with special needs. Both studies use the CIPP evaluation model as an analytical framework, which allows for assessment of context, input, process, and product aspects. Thus, both view education as a system involving policies, resources, implementation, and outcomes. Furthermore, their primary goal is to improve the equity and effectiveness of education, ensuring that efforts are oriented toward equity and quality education for all groups in society.</p>	<p>unequal access to education in remote areas. Meanwhile, the study "Evaluation of Inclusive Education Policy in Indonesia" focuses more on inclusive education policies for children with special needs (ABK), without highlighting the role of the legislative body specifically. In terms of context, this current study is local and specific to Bali, while previous studies, national in scale, analyzed policy more generally. Furthermore, this study incorporates an adaptive governance perspective, namely how policies and implementation are adapted to real conditions on the ground, while research on inclusive education focuses more on evaluating the effectiveness of policies and program implementation.</p>
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Source: Researcher Processed Data (2025)

Framework

The conceptual framework in this study was developed to illustrate the logical relationship between the phenomenon of unequal access to education in remote areas and the implementation of adaptive governance by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD, and how the effectiveness of this policy can be evaluated using the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model developed by Daniel L. Stufflebeam. Conceptually, this study is based on the assumption that unequal access to education in remote areas is not solely caused by limited resources, but also by limitations in policy governance mechanisms that are not yet fully adaptive to the social and geographical dynamics of the region. In this context, adaptive governance exists as a public governance paradigm that emphasizes the importance of institutional flexibility, collaboration between stakeholders, and the ability to respond to change sustainably. Of these four components, the CIPP model serves as a conceptual instrument that bridges the theory of adaptive governance with the practice of regional education policy. The logical relationship between variables indicates that adaptive governance is a dynamic approach, and its effectiveness can only be fully understood when viewed from the context, input, process, and outcome of the policy. Thus, this research framework forms a systematic line of thought, starting from identifying the problem of educational inequality, implementing adaptive governance principles by the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD), and conducting an evaluative analysis using the

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CIPP model. This approach is expected to produce a comprehensive picture of the effectiveness of adaptive governance in education, while also providing an empirical basis for formulating more responsive, inclusive, and sustainable policy recommendations.

METHOD

The research approach, design, and procedures were systematic. This study employed a qualitative approach to analyze the implementation of *adaptive governance* by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to unequal access to education in remote areas. The data used included primary and secondary data obtained through interviews, observation, and documentation. Informants were selected purposively based on their relevance to the research focus. Data analysis was conducted through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing, combined with the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model evaluation framework. This study employed a qualitative descriptive design aimed at deeply understanding the process, dynamics, and meaning of the implementation of *adaptive governance* in regional education policy. This design was chosen because the research was not oriented towards hypothesis testing, but rather towards a holistic exploration of social phenomena.

Research analysis uses the CIPP model, which includes:

- a. Context : examines the social, geographical, and policy conditions underlying educational inequality;
- b. Input : examines the resources and policy strategies used;
- c. Process : analyzing the implementation and coordination of policies;
- d. Product : evaluating the results and impact of policies on educational equality.

This research is flexible and iterative, with data collection and analysis conducted simultaneously. Data were obtained through field observations in several remote areas of Bali and in-depth interviews with key informants, such as members of Commission IV of the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD), officials from the Education Office, and educators. The interviews were semi-structured to obtain in-depth and contextual data. The data used in this study is descriptive qualitative data, consisting of words, actions, and documents that describe social phenomena contextually.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results and Findings

Context

This indicator refers to the conditions, background, and circumstances under which a program or policy is implemented. Context serves as the basis for understanding why a program is necessary, with an emphasis on identifying needs, problems, opportunities, and environmental characteristics that influence its implementation. More specifically, context evaluation aims to identify gaps between expected conditions and actual conditions on the ground. This includes analysis of social, economic, geographic, institutional, and relevant policy aspects. By understanding the context comprehensively, program objectives can be formulated more precisely and responsively to actual needs. Therefore, *context* in the CIPP model serves as the initial foundation that provides direction for program implementation, ensuring that the program is designed to truly address the problems and needs faced and maintains strong relevance to the environmental conditions in which it is implemented.

Observations conducted by researchers found that there are schools in remote areas in Bali Province whose building infrastructure is in quite worrying condition. Most of the schools visited that are the result of the findings in this study are schools at the elementary and secondary levels of education, while the biggest problem found in the upper education level is related to the standardization of the Education curriculum. To maintain the objectivity of this research, all forms of documentation in this study will be mentioned only the exact location of the research school, this is done to ensure the safety of teachers and all school staff. In observations conducted in Klungkung, there are schools that are in very worrying condition. The lack of classrooms means that the UKS, which should function as a health center for students, is instead used as a classroom.

Figure 1. UKS which is used as a classroom at an elementary school in Klungkung Regency

Source: Researcher Documentation, 2026

Furthermore, researchers found a school with severely damaged classrooms that had not been properly maintained. This damage included damage to the roof, rendering three classrooms unusable. The damaged building forced fifth- and second-grade students to study in the same classroom, disrupting their learning. This damage occurred at an elementary school in Karangasem Regency.

Figure 2. Classroom building that suffered severe damage to the roof in Karangasem Regency

Source: Researcher Documentation, 2026

In the context of unequal access to education in remote areas of Bangli Regency, the condition of educational facilities and infrastructure still shows significant limitations. Based on field observations, the learning process takes place in classrooms with very simple facilities, where the desks and chairs used by students appear to be uneven and some are worn. In addition, students attend without wearing school uniforms, indicating both economic limitations and weak standards for meeting basic educational needs. This situation reflects that the learning environment does not fully meet the standards for basic education eligibility, both in terms of physical facilities and support for student

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identity and discipline. The condition of the learning space with minimal facilities, and the lack of basic attributes such as school uniforms, indicates a clear gap between urban and remote areas in terms of access to and quality of educational services. Furthermore, these conditions indicate that basic educational needs in this region have not been optimally met, thus requiring more contextual and adaptive policy interventions. In this case, the role of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD is crucial in responding to the reality of this inequality through an adaptive governance approach that can adapt policies to specific conditions on the ground.

Figure 3. Classroom of a school in a remote area in Bangli Regency

Source: *Researcher Documentation, 2026*

In this study, the researcher also presented *contextual elements* in the form of direct quotations from an interview with the Chairman of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD, I Nyoman Suwirta. The interview was conducted on April 8, 2026. In this interview, I Nyoman Suwirta explained that education in Bali Province still experiences disparities, especially in remote areas.

"We even went into the field and found one school with 60 classes but only 24 classrooms. As a result, the remaining classes were forced to implement online learning. This will be very difficult and challenging for character development in the affected students, especially those in underserved areas."

Based on this, the context aspect within the CIPP model framework demonstrates a strong alignment with the principles of adaptive governance, which emphasize the importance of sensitivity to local dynamics and the ability to flexibly respond to environmental change and complexity. From this perspective, the mapping conducted not only serves as an instrument for identifying problems but also as a basis for formulating responsive policy directions based on the real needs of the community. Therefore, the mapping efforts carried out by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD can be understood as a manifestation of institutional capacity in internalizing the principles of adaptive governance, particularly in terms of the ability to read the context accurately and comprehensively. This ultimately has implications for improving the quality of the resulting policy responses, making them more adaptive, relevant, and having a higher level of targeted accuracy in addressing inequality in access to education in remote areas.

Input

In terms of input indicators, the findings of this study comprehensively reveal the condition, availability, and readiness of various resources that serve as the primary foundation for implementing policy responses by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD. This indicator plays a crucial role, considering that the quality of the input will significantly determine the direction and effectiveness of the process and the resulting policy outcomes. Therefore, the presentation in this section is aimed at providing a comprehensive picture of the extent to which supporting elements have been provided and optimized in responding to unequal access to education in remote areas. The findings in the input indicators focus not only on quantitative aspects but also encompass the quality and relevance of each available resource. This includes human resource capacity, particularly the role and competence of DPRD

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members in carrying out legislative, oversight, and budgeting functions; the adequacy and distribution of education budget allocations; the availability of supporting facilities and infrastructure; and the existence of regulations and policies that serve as the operational basis for program implementation.

Based on the results of a literature review referring to various regional planning documents, budget reports, and educational statistics, the input aspect in addressing inequality in access to education in Bali Province shows a condition generally characterized by the availability of relatively adequate resources quantitatively, but not yet fully effective qualitatively in addressing the specific needs of remote areas. This condition indicates that the fundamental problem lies not in limited resources, but in the dimensions of governance, distribution, and policy sensitivity to the local context. From a budget perspective, the Bali Provincial Government demonstrates a strong fiscal commitment to the education sector, as reflected in the proportion of budget allocation that consistently exceeds the minimum limit of 20% as required by national policy. In recent years, the education budget allocation in Bali has ranged from IDR 1.9 trillion to IDR 2.5 trillion, or equivalent to approximately 27% to 38% of the total regional budget. This amount normatively indicates a substantial regional fiscal capacity to support equity and improve the quality of education, including for areas with limited access.

Process

Within the framework of program evaluation using the CIPP model, the process aspect plays an important role in explaining how a policy or program is actually implemented in the field, including the working mechanisms, interaction patterns between actors, and the dynamics of policy implementation in responding to emerging problems. In this study, the process aspect is not only interpreted as an administrative stage in the implementation of education policies in Bali Province, but also as a dynamic and adaptive interaction space between policy actors, especially Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD, with the factual conditions at the level of educational units that face inequality in access to education, especially in remote areas. Therefore, the analysis in this section focuses on examining how the process of absorbing aspirations, providing policy direction to schools, coordination mechanisms with the Education Office, and the process of monitoring policies and budgeting are carried out, so that it can be seen to what extent the implementation of these policies reflects the principles of adaptive governance, such as flexibility, responsiveness, collaboration, and the ability to learn policies in facing the complexity of educational problems in the region. Based on the results of field studies through in-depth interviews with Agung Bagus Tri Candra Arka who also has a role in the DPRD Budget Agency, as well as data triangulation through interviews with one of the school principals in Jembrana Regency, it is known that the process of implementing the functions of supervision, budgeting, and facilitation of educational policies by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to inequality in access to education in remote areas does not only take place formally-administratively, but also involves direct interaction with educational units in the field. This finding indicates that the ongoing policy process has reflected efforts to strengthen two-way communication between policy makers and implementers at the school level. On the one hand, the DPRD plays a role as an actor that directs and monitors school needs to align with the regional planning system, while on the other hand, schools are given a space for participation to convey the factual conditions they face.

Product (Product)

Within the context component of the CIPP model, this study's findings indicate that educational inequality in remote areas of Bali Province remains a complex structural issue, influenced by geographic limitations, the unequal distribution of educational resources, and the relatively vulnerable socioeconomic conditions of the community. This situation creates an unbalanced educational landscape between urban and remote areas, both in terms of access, processes, and policy support.

Based on an interview with a school principal in a remote area of Bangli Regency, the educational situation is described as still facing significant limitations, particularly in terms of infrastructure and teaching staff. The interview stated:

"In general, we've felt the government and the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) showing concern, particularly through assistance with facilities and programs to improve the quality of education. We've already received several facilities, such as assistance with classroom renovations, distribution of learning supplies, and teacher capacity-building programs, and these have significantly assisted the school in carrying out the learning process."

This statement demonstrates that substantively, there have been positive achievements from the policies initiated by the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD), particularly in the oversight and budgeting functions through Commission IV, which have begun to address the basic needs of educational institutions in remote

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areas. However, the principal also emphasized that these achievements are not yet fully distributed and that there are still a number of limitations in their implementation. He stated that,

"Although assistance and attention have been provided, not all school needs have been fully met. For example, some classrooms still haven't been repaired, and some operational needs, such as technology-based learning media, are still very limited. Furthermore, the aid that arrives sometimes doesn't align with the school's most pressing priorities, requiring us to readjust its use on the ground."

This indicates that despite positive achievements, the effectiveness of policies in reaching all dimensions of the community's educational needs is still not optimal. In the context of adaptive governance implemented by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD, these findings indicate that the achievements made can be categorized as quite good in the initial stages, particularly in terms of increasing policy attention, distribution of educational aid, and strengthening cross-sectoral coordination. The DPRD has demonstrated an active role in promoting the agenda of educational equality through legislative, budgetary, and oversight functions that have begun to reach remote areas. However, the findings also indicate several shortcomings that still need to be addressed, particularly regarding the accuracy of program targeting, the sustainability of interventions, and the equitable distribution of educational resources. Furthermore, there remains a gap between formulated policies and the reality of implementation at the school and community levels, indicating that the adaptive governance process is still in the stage of strengthening responsive capacity.

Analysis of Findings

This section outlines an in-depth analysis of research findings obtained from interviews with school principals and parents in remote areas, contextualized within the role of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD within the framework of adaptive governance. This analysis serves not only to describe empirical data but also to interpret the broader meaning of these findings from the perspective of responsive, adaptive, and equitable public service-oriented education governance. Using the CIPP Model as an analytical framework, the discussion focuses on how the context of educational inequality in remote areas shapes policy needs, how policy inputs and interventions carried out by the Bali Provincial DPRD are designed and implemented, and the extent to which the policy adaptation process is able to respond to empirical realities on the ground. At this stage, the findings are positioned not only as factual information but also as a basis for evaluating the coherence between policy design, implementation mechanisms, and the subjective experiences of stakeholders at the school and community levels. Furthermore, this analysis also positions field findings as a reflection of the dynamics of the relationship between the state and society in the context of education in remote areas, where structural limitations, unequal access, and variations in institutional capacity are factors that simultaneously influence policy effectiveness. Therefore, this section is aimed at providing a critical interpretation of the extent to which adaptive governance implemented by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD is able to bridge this gap, while also identifying aspects that still require strengthening in order to realize more inclusive and equitable educational equality.

Context Findings Analysis

Based on the overall findings on the contextual aspects of the CIPP model, it can be analyzed that educational inequality in remote areas of Bali Province is not a stand-alone phenomenon, but rather the result of an accumulation of various structural factors that interact in a complex manner. Field findings indicate that educational problems in remote areas are not only related to the physical limitations of facilities and infrastructure, but also reflect imbalances in the distribution of educational services, limited school institutional capacity, and the existence of geographical and socio-economic barriers that form a systemic pattern of unequal access to education. Observations in Klungkung, Karangasem, and Bangli Regencies indicate that the condition of educational infrastructure remains far below the minimum standards for basic education. The use of UKS rooms as classrooms in Klungkung indicates the emergency condition of educational facilities that have shifted from their ideal function. Spaces that should function as school health units are instead converted into learning spaces due to limited classroom space. This condition directly reflects the pressure on infrastructure capacity that is not commensurate with the number of students or the need for available learning spaces. A more critical finding emerged in Karangasem Regency, where severe damage to building structures, particularly classroom roofs, rendered some classrooms permanently non-functional. This situation led to the merging of classes across grades, such as grades 2 and 5, which had to study in the same room. This situation not only impacted learning effectiveness but also disrupted curriculum differentiation and pedagogical strategies that should be tailored to the developmental level of students. In this context, it can be analyzed that the infrastructure gap has had direct implications for the quality of the educational process itself. Meanwhile, in Bangli Regency, the problems identified were more multidimensional, namely a combination of limited physical facilities and the socio-

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economic conditions of students. The unevenness of desks and chairs, as well as the worn condition of learning facilities, indicated low standards of educational facility maintenance. Furthermore, students' failure to wear school uniforms indicated family economic constraints and the suboptimal fulfillment of basic educational needs. This situation demonstrates that educational inequality occurs not only at the school level but also at the household level, the primary support unit for children's education. Thus, it can be concluded that the contextual aspects of this study reveal three main layers of problems: inadequate educational infrastructure, vulnerable socio-economic communities, and policy governance, which still faces challenges in terms of implementation effectiveness. On the other hand, there are also positive indications in the form of institutional awareness from the Bali Provincial DPRD in identifying and mapping problems directly in the field. However, the balance between understanding the context and policy response capabilities remains a major challenge that needs to be strengthened within an adaptive governance framework so that educational inequality in remote areas can be addressed more comprehensively, systematically, and sustainably.

Input Findings Analysis

Based on the findings of the input indicators within the CIPP Model framework, it can be analyzed that the problem of unequal access to education in remote areas of Bali Province stems not from a lack of resources, but rather from inaccurate design, distribution, and utilization of available policy inputs. Normatively, the availability of an education budget ranging from 27% to 38% of the total Regional Budget (APBD) indicates a strong fiscal commitment from the Bali Provincial Government to the education sector. However, upon closer analysis, this budget size does not fully reflect its effectiveness in addressing real needs on the ground, particularly in areas with high levels of isolation such as Bangli and Karangasem Regencies. This condition indicates a gap between fiscal capacity and allocation effectiveness. The budgeting pattern, which is still aggregative and tends to be administrative, results in resource distribution that does not fully consider the principle of needs-based equity. As a result, areas with higher levels of geographical difficulty do not receive proportional budget affirmation. In this context, it can be analyzed that policy inputs are not fully oriented towards a regional differentiation approach, resulting in inequality in implementation capacity at the school level. The dominance of operational expenditures over capital expenditures indicates a budget structure that does not fully support the transformation of education services in remote areas. When the majority of the budget is absorbed by routine expenditures such as salaries and allowances, fiscal space for strategic interventions such as school infrastructure development, providing access to educational transportation, and rehabilitating learning facilities is limited.

This condition indicates that structurally, budget inputs have not been optimally directed to address the root causes of unequal access to education, but rather remain focused on the sustainability of the existing system. From an institutional perspective, the role of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD as a budgeting and oversight actor demonstrates a strategic role in determining the direction of education policy. However, findings indicate that the integration of field needs data with the decision-making process is still not optimal. This indicates that the institutional representation function has not fully translated the complexity of education issues in remote areas into operational and adaptive policy designs. When analyzed from an adaptive governance perspective, the current input conditions reflect a suboptimal implementation of the principles of responsiveness, flexibility, and policy learning. Despite the relatively large amount of resources available, the main weakness lies in the system's limited ability to dynamically adjust resource allocation to specific regional needs. In other words, the input system remains static, not adaptive. Thus, the analysis of the input aspect shows three main interrelated problems, namely: first, the mismatch between the budget size and the effectiveness of needs-based distribution; second, the inequality in the distribution and quality of human resources in education between regions; and third, the less than optimal institutional capacity in integrating empirical data into the policy process.

Process Findings Analysis

Based on the findings of the process aspect within the CIPP Model framework, it can be analyzed that the implementation of education policy by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to unequal access to education in remote areas shows a shift from a formal-administrative governance pattern to a more interactive and field-based approach. The implementation process does not only stop at structural mechanisms such as meetings, formal aspiration absorption, or budget discussions, but also involves direct intervention through field visits to educational units, which serve as a space for empirical validation of existing data and policy proposals. From the results of interviews with DPRD actors and schools, it is clear that the policy process has contained elements of direct engagement between policymakers and policy implementers at the micro level. The DPRD's involvement in going directly to schools reflects an effort to reduce information asymmetry between the policy level and the reality on the

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ground. In this context, the process is no longer one-way, but has begun to form a two-way communication pattern that allows for a more substantive exchange of information. The DPRD not only plays a role as a recipient of aspirations, but also as an actor that provides normative direction regarding the priority needs of schools, which then becomes part of the policy selection process in the regional planning and budgeting cycle. Thus, it can be concluded that the process aspect of this study demonstrates significant progress in implementing more participatory and field-based education policies. However, this process still faces major challenges in terms of institutionalizing adaptive mechanisms, consistent implementation across regions, and strengthening the coordination system between policy actors. Therefore, in the context of improving adaptive governance, strengthening procedural and institutional aspects is necessary so that the policy process does not rely solely on actor initiatives but becomes part of a stable, measurable, and sustainable governance system that addresses educational inequality in remote areas.

Product Findings Analysis

Based on the findings on the product aspect within the CIPP Model framework, it can be analyzed that the policy achievements generated through the role of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to educational inequality in remote areas show mixed outcomes, namely there is real progress but has not fully achieved the ideal conditions expected in the principle of educational equality. Substantively, the resulting policy products can be seen from the increased attention and intervention of local governments to the basic needs of educational units in remote areas. This is reflected in the provision of infrastructure assistance, distribution of learning equipment, and programs to increase the capacity of educators that have been felt by schools. In this context, the policy output shows that the institutional function of the DPRD, particularly through Commission IV, has produced a tangible form of education policy advocacy that is not only normative, but also begins to touch on the implementation aspects in the field. Thus, initially it can be said that there are positive results in the form of increased access to basic education support. Therefore, from the perspective of the CIPP model on the product aspect, it can be concluded that the policy results of Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to educational inequality in remote areas are progressive but not yet final. While there have been positive achievements demonstrating increased attention and concrete interventions in the education sector, fundamental deficiencies remain in terms of equitable distribution of benefits, effective resource distribution, and equitable outcomes. Therefore, policy outcomes in this context can be understood as transitional outcomes in the adaptive governance process, shifting from reactive policies to more systemic and sustainable ones. To achieve this ideal situation, strengthening the accuracy of policy targets, consistent implementation, and integrating locally-based evaluations is necessary. This ensures that policy outcomes do not merely focus on administrative outputs but actually produce substantive outcomes in the form of equitable access to education throughout Bali Province.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis using the CIPP Model, the implementation of *adaptive governance* by Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD in responding to educational inequality in remote areas indicates that policy governance is still in a transitional phase, from an administrative-reactive pattern to a more adaptive and contextual approach, but is not yet fully institutionally mature. In terms of context, educational inequality in Bali is a structural problem influenced by geographic factors, uneven distribution of resources, limited infrastructure, and the socio-economic conditions of the community. This reflects that educational problems in remote areas are closely related to the issue of development equity. In terms of input, there is a paradox between the availability of relatively adequate resources and the less than optimal effectiveness of distribution. Budget allocation and teaching staff are still not fully based on regional needs, resulting in inaccurate policy interventions. In terms of process, Commission IV of the Bali Provincial DPRD has demonstrated efforts towards more participatory and data-driven governance, particularly through field visits and direct interactions with educational units. However, this process is still not systematically institutionalized and tends to depend on actor dynamics. In terms of product, the resulting policies have had initial impacts, such as increased attention to remote areas and the distribution of educational assistance. However, these achievements remain at the output level and have not yet resulted in significant changes in reducing educational disparities across the board. Overall, the implementation of *adaptive governance* has shown progress, particularly in its sensitivity to local contexts and strengthening of policy representation. However, its implementation still requires strengthening, particularly in terms of institutional consistency, policy integration, and the ability to respond more appropriately and sustainably to local needs. Therefore, the main challenge lies in aligning policy design with the reality of implementation to achieve more inclusive and equitable educational equality.

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